

GRID SEARCH-DRIVEN HYPERPARAMETER OPTIMIZATION FOR RANDOM FOREST MODEL IN TEXT ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Random Forest, a widely used ensemble learning algorithm, exhibits strong classification performance; however, its accuracy and computational efficiency are highly dependent on appropriate hyperparameter tuning. To address this, the research employs a systematic grid search optimization approach to identify the optimal combination of key Random Forest parameters. Experimental results demonstrate that the optimized Random Forest model achieved an accuracy of 98.40%, outperforming the baseline model across all key performance metrics, including precision, recall, and F1-score, with improvements of up to 0.31%. Notably, the optimized configuration also reduced training time by approximately 83.72%, underscoring the significant computational efficiency gained through systematic tuning. These findings clearly prove that structured grid search optimization not only enhances predictive performance but also reduces computational cost, making it a robust and interpretable approach for machine learning model refinement.

Keywords: Random Forest, Grid Search, Hyperparameter, Classification, Optimization, Machine Learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning (ML) has become a transformative technology in data-driven problem solving, offering innovative approaches to classification, prediction, and pattern recognition across multiple disciplines. Among the various algorithms, Random Forest (RF) stands out as one of the most reliable ensemble methods, valued for its robustness, interpretability, and effectiveness in handling both structured and unstructured data (Contreras et al., 2021). However, the predictive performance of RF is significantly influenced by its hyperparameter configuration, such as the number of trees, maximum features, and minimum samples required to split a node. Suboptimal settings can lead to overfitting, underfitting, or high computational costs, limiting the model's generalization ability (Rohman et al., 2025).

Hyperparameter optimization (HPO) is thus a critical step in ML model development. Grid search, a systematic and exhaustive search method, remains a widely used and effective approach for hyperparameter tuning. Evaluating all possible combinations within a predefined parameter space ensures a comprehensive search for the optimal configuration (SijiGeorgeC & B.Sumathi, 2020). Despite being computationally intensive, grid search offers reproducibility and consistency, providing valuable insights into parameter sensitivity and model behavior. Optimized hyperparameters can significantly improve model performance metrics, including precision, recall, and F1-score, as well as reduce training time and computational overhead

(Zhu et al., 2022). However, different hyperparameter configurations collectively affect both accuracy and computational efficiency, especially in high-dimensional or text-based datasets (Suryadi et al., 2024).

Additionally, while emerging methods such as Bayesian optimization and genetic algorithms have shown potential, systematic grid search-based optimization remains a foundational and interpretable approach to benchmarking performance across models (Elgeldawi et al., 2021).

Therefore, this research focuses on optimizing the Random Forest model using a grid search-driven hyperparameter tuning approach to improve classification efficiency and performance. The study systematically explores the influence of critical hyperparameters on model accuracy and computational time, thereby contributing to a deeper understanding of how grid search optimization can enhance model reliability, scalability, and resource utilization across text classification tasks.

2. METHODOLOGY

The process flow of the optimized method on hyperparameter tuning using grid search is shown in Figure 1. The Python programming language was used to build the model and execute it in a Jupyter Notebook v6.4.8 environment. To accelerate ML tasks at each stage of the model workflow, the libraries of Scikit-learn, NumPy, and Pandas are also employed.

Fig 1: RF model process flow

2.1 Data Preprocessing

The dataset consists of 3,756 Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) sequence samples, with each sample containing a length of 415 base pairs belonging to one of 82 classes. The raw dataset, represented as a string of characters, is converted and processed using *K-mer* counting and the

bag-of-words technique using *CountVectorizer* to modify the data to be suitable as training input to an ML classification model, as shown in Figure 2. A *k-mer* in the DNA sequence is a sequence of k consecutive nucleotides. It breaks the nucleotides into possible substrings of length k , where k is a user-defined parameter. *CountVectorizer* is a text feature extraction method that converts a collection of text documents into a matrix of token counts. A bag-of-words approach is utilized, which disregards the order of the words in the text and only considers the frequency of the words. Subsequently, the dataset is divided randomly into 80% training and 20% testing sets.

Fig 2: Data preprocessing

A data augmentation (Kircher et al., 2022) is applied to the dataset to provide more diverse examples for the model to learn. The DNA sequence data may contain inherent noise due to various factors, such as sequencing errors or biological variations. Adding noise during data augmentation helps the model become more robust to such noise in the input data. Incorporating augmented datasets can enhance the classification accuracy of the trained models (Shorten & Khoshgoftaar, 2019) and can aid in mitigating the risk of overfitting (Taylor & Nitschke, 2018). A noise ratio is set, which represents the proportion of nucleotides that are randomly changed.

2.2 Hyperparameter configuration in Random Forest

The RF algorithm is a type of ensemble learning algorithm based on decision trees (Breiman, 2001). It is composed of two main parts: the random sampling of the data and features, and the decision construction. The first part ensures that each tree in the forest is trained on a different subset of the data and features, making them more diverse. The second part constructs a decision tree based on the training data and is used to make predictions. These decision trees are independent, and errors are reduced collectively, leading to more reliable and precise classification results.

In the optimization process, three hyperparameters are configured, namely, the number of trees (*n_estimators*), the maximum number of features (*max_features*), and a minimum number of samples required to split an internal node (*min_samples_split*) as shown in Table 1. The number of trees represents the number of decision trees that the RF model built during the training. The maximum features represent the number of input features that the RF model considers at each split in the decision tree. The minimum sample split ensures that a node is not split if the number of samples in that node is less than the specified value.

Table 1: Hyperparameters configured in Random Forest

Hyperparameters	Range	Step
n_estimators	[20, 80]	20
max_features	[2, 30]	2
min_samples_split	[2, 20]	5

2.3 Grid Search Algorithm

The process of finding the most suitable hyperparameters for a given dataset in a learning algorithm is referred to as tuning. First, a hyperparameter configuration space is created, then an RF classifier is built by combining the sets of hyperparameters within the space. Next, the RF classifier with hyperparameters is optimized using a grid search approach, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig 3: Grid search method to tune hyperparameters

Grid search is a decision-theoretic method that exhaustively searches the optimal hyperparameter configuration within a predefined domain. In the grid search approach, the hyperparameter configuration space is generated by taking the Cartesian product of the value set for each hyperparameter combination.

To identify the optimal hyperparameter, the following processes are performed:

- Step 1: Define the initial range of hyperparameter values and their corresponding step sizes, then generate a grid containing all possible hyperparameter combinations.
- Step 2: Split the dataset into training and validation sets. Apply cross-validation to evaluate the performance of each hyperparameter combination.
- Step 3: For each hyperparameter combination, the model is trained using the specified hyperparameter values, and its performance is evaluated on the validation data.
- Step 4: Identify the hyperparameter combination with the highest score. Based on the results, narrow the range of hyperparameter values and adjust the step sizes accordingly. Repeat Step 3 until the optimal hyperparameters are found, and then train the final model using these best parameters.
- Step 5: Assess the performance of the optimized model on the test dataset using the selected hyperparameters.

2.4 Evaluation Metrics

The performance of the optimized RF classification model is evaluated using the efficiency metrics: precision, recall, F1-score, and accuracy. These metrics are calculated as follows:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (1)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (2)$$

$$F1 - score = \frac{2 * Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (3)$$

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FN + TN + FP} \quad (4)$$

The precision is the ratio of correctly predicted positive samples to the total number of positive samples predicted by the model. It is calculated as the ratio of true positives (TP) to the sum of TP and false positives (FP).

Recall, also known as sensitivity or TP rate, is the ratio of correctly predicted positive samples to the total number of positive samples in the dataset. It is calculated as the ratio of TP to the sum of TP and false negatives (FN).

The F1-score, which is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, considers both precision and recall and is a good indicator of the overall classifier performance. It is calculated as 2 times the product of precision and recall divided by the sum of precision and recall. Additionally, the accuracy measures the proportion of correctly classified samples (both TP and TN) out of the total number of samples.

The process of training a model can be computationally intensive, especially for large datasets or complex models. Thus, it is important to evaluate the performance time or computational time of the model training process. The performance time or computational time is the time taken by the model to complete the training process. This metric is important because it provides an estimate of the time required to train the model and can help in determining the feasibility of using the model in a real-world setting. This metric is calculated as:

$$Training_{time} = End_{time} - Start_{time} \quad (5)$$

The model is trained on a system equipped with 32GB RAM, a 10th Generation Intel Core i7 processor, and a graphics card with 6GB NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060 memory and a refresh rate of 144Hz.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The model is trained and tested using the DNA sequence dataset. Table 2 shows the optimal hyperparameters obtained by the grid search algorithm. The optimum value indicates that the best performance was achieved at 60 trees, 22 features, and 4 sample splits at each node with an accuracy score of 98.40%. The result indicates that the optimized RF hyperparameter values achieved better performance with fewer decision trees, a smaller subset of features, and a sample split.

Table 2: Optimal hyperparameters

Hyperparameters	Range-Step	Baseline RF Value	Optimized RF Value
n_estimators	[20, 80, 20]	100	60
max_features	[2, 30, 2]	sqrt	22
min_samples_split	[4, 20, 5]	2	4

Table 3 shows the efficiency metric comparison results of the optimized RF and baseline RF models. The optimized RF achieved a slight improvement in all the metrics compared to the baseline RF. The largest difference is observed in the F1 score, which is 0.31%. The small differences in the other metrics, such as 0.27% accuracy, 0.24% precision, and 0.27% recall, are indicative of improved overall model performance. The differences are relatively small, indicating that the optimized RF performed slightly better than the baseline RF.

Table 3: Performance comparison of optimized and baseline Random Forest

Metrics	Baseline RF (%)	Optimized RF (%)
Accuracy	99.069	99.335
Precision	99.155	99.398
Recall	99.069	99.335
F1-score	98.996	99.309

In processing time, the optimized RF model was 35.69883 seconds faster than the baseline RF to train on the given dataset with approximately 83.72% reduction, as shown in Figure 4. This improvement in training time is significant, especially when dealing with larger datasets or when using more complex models.

Fig 4: Training time comparison of optimized and baseline Random Forest

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study presented an optimized Random Forest classification framework for fish DNA sequence data using a grid search-driven hyperparameter tuning approach. By systematically exploring combinations of the number of trees, maximum number of features, and minimum samples required for node splitting, the grid search algorithm successfully identified the optimal hyperparameter configuration. The resulting RF model achieved an accuracy of 98.40%, outperforming the baseline model across all evaluation metrics, notwithstanding modest but meaningful gains. Notably, the optimized model achieved an 83.72% reduction in training time, demonstrating that hyperparameter tuning can simultaneously enhance predictive performance and computational efficiency. The findings feature the importance of rigorous hyperparameter optimization in developing robust ML models for genomic classification tasks. Treating DNA sequences as textual data through *k-mer*-based vectorization proved effective, enabling the RF classifier to capture meaningful patterns from genetic inputs. The performance improvements observed in this study emphasize the potential of grid search as a reliable and interpretable optimization strategy for bioinformatics applications.

Future research could extend this work by comparing grid search with adaptive optimization algorithms such as Bayesian optimization, Hyperband, or reinforcement learning-based tuning approaches to further improve scalability and automation (Rimal et al., 2024). Finally, this study contributes to the broader understanding of how structured search optimization enhances ensemble learning performance and sets a foundation for more efficient hyperparameter tuning methodologies in machine learning research.

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